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Texture Analysis for the Classification of Carotid Plaques

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Abstract

The objective of this work is to develop a computer aided system which will facilitate the automated characterization of carotid plaques recorded from high resolution ultrasound images for the identification of individuals with asymptomatic carotid stenosis at risk of stroke. The system consists of the following four modules: (i) image standardization, (ii) image segmentation, (iii) feature extraction and selection, (iv) plaque classification. The images are standardised using blood and adventitia as reference, and the plaque is identified and manually outlined. In the feature extraction module, nine different texture feature sets and shape parameters (a total of 61 features) are extracted from the segmented plaque image in order to be used for the plaque classification. The plaques should be classified into one of the following types: (i) symptomatic because of ipsilateral hemispheric symptoms, or (ii) asymptomatic because they were not connected with ipsilateral hemispheric events. For the classification the unsupervised learning neural network algorithm self-organising feature map (SOFM) is used. A total of 37 (24 symptomatic + 13 asymptomatic) ultrasound images of carotid plaques were examined and their features were extracted. The statistics of all features extracted for the two groups indicate a high degree of overlap, making the separation of the two groups a difficult task. The SOFM classifier was trained and evaluated with the ten different feature sets. Best feature set was found to be the fractals set with a classification success rate of 65%. Due to the complexity of the problem and the high degree of overlap of the texture features it is necessary that the results be verified with more data.

1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of this work is to develop a computer aided system which will facilitate the automated characterization of carotid plaques recorded from high resolution ultrasound images (duplex scanning and color flow imaging). This work is part of an European Union project (Biomed 2 Program - PL 950629) carried out in centers all over Europe and coordinated by the St. Mary's Hospital. The aim of the project is to evaluate the value of noninvasive investigations in the identification of individuals with Asymptomatic Carotid Stenosis at Risk of Stroke (ACRS).

There is evidence that carotid endarterectomy in patients with asymptomatic carotid stenosis will reduce the incidence of stroke. However, a large number of patients is operated unnecessarily. Twenty patients have to be operated in order to prevent one stroke in 5 years, or 100 patients to prevent one stroke in one year. Therefore it is necessary to identify patients at high risk (>4% stroke incidence p.a.) which will be considered for carotid endarterectomy, and patients at low risk (>1% p.a.) which will be spared from an unnecessary, expensive and often dangerous operation. There are indications that the morphology of atherosclerotic carotid plaques, obtained by high resolution ultrasound imaging, have prognostic implications [1]. Smooth surface, echogenicity and a homogenous texture are characteristics of stable plaques, whereas irregular surface, echolucency and a heterogenous texture are characteristics of potentially unstable plaques.

The computer aided classification of carotid plaques will contribute towards a more standardized and accurate methodology for the assessment of carotid plaques. This will greatly help in enhancing the significance of noninvasive cerebrovascular tests in the identification of asymptomatic carotid stenosis at risk of stroke. The proposed system should be able, based on extracted texture feature and shape parameters, to automatically classify plaques into one of the following types : (i) symptomatic because of ipsilateral hemispheric symptoms and (ii) asymptomatic because they were not connected with ipsilateral hemispheric events. The aim is to identify patients at risk of stroke.

The modules of the computer aided system for carotid plaque classification are the following: (i) image standardization, (ii) plaque segmentation (iii) feature extraction and selection, (iv) plaque classification. Figure 1 illustrates the flowchart of the computer aided system for carotid plaque classification.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the computer aided system for carotid plaque classification.

2 MATERIAL

Patients with greater than 50% asymptomatic internal carotid artery stenosis are collected from different centers and send to the coordinator. Imaging data are quantified based on the protocols suggested by the project [2]. Patients will be followed up for three years with the main endpoint being stroke. Ultrasound scans were performed using duplex scanning and B-mode scan settings were adjusted so that the maximum dynamic range was used with a linear post processing curve. The position of the probe was adjusted so that the ultrasonic beam was vertical to the artery wall. The TGC-curve was adjusted to produce uniform intensity of echoes on the screen, but it was vertical in the lumen of the artery where attenuation in blood was minimal so that echogenicity of the far wall was the same as that of the near wall. The overall gain was set so that the appearance of the plaque was judged to be optimal. In this study a total of 37 (24 symptomatic + 13 asymptomatic) ultrasound images of carotid atherosclerotic plaques were available for examination.

3 METHOD

3.1 Image Standardization

Before processing, the images were standardised manually by adjusting the image so that the median gray level value of the blood was between 15-20 and the median gray level value of the adventitia (artery wall) was between 180-200. The scale of the gray level of the images ranges from 0 to 255. This standardisation using blood and adventitia as reference points was necessary in order to extract comparable results when processing images obtained by different operators and different equipment.

3.2 Plaque Segmentation

After the image standardisation, the plaque was identified and manually outlined by the expert physician. The identification and the segmentation of the plaque is a difficult task especially when the plaques are highly echolucent. The segmentation of the plaque is significantly facilitated when a color image is available indicating the blood flow. All 37 plaque images used in this study were outlined using their corresponding color blood flow images. This guarantees that the plaques were correctly outlined which is essential for extracting correct texture features characterizing the plaque and for reaching correct conclusions about the capability to classify them. Figure 2 illustrates an ultrasound image with the outline of the carotid plaque.

Fig. 2 An ultrasound image with the outline of the carotid plaque.

3.3 Feature Extraction and Selection

Texture features and shape parameters were extracted from the manually segmented plaque image in order to be used for the classification of the carotid plaques. Texture contains important information which is used by humans for the interpretation and the analysis of many types of images. It is especially useful for the analysis of natural scenes since they mostly consist of textured surfaces. Texture refers to the spatial interrelationships and arrangement of the basic elements of an image [3]. Visually, these spatial interrelationships and arrangements of the image pixels are seen as variations in the intensity patterns or gray tones. Therefore texture features have to be derived from the gray tones of the image. Although it is easy for humans to recognize texture, it is quite a difficult task to be defined, and subsequently to be interpreted by digital computers. In this study, features containing information about plaques textural characteristics like first order statistics, gray-tone linear dependencies (linear structure), coarseness, contrast, roughness and the complexity of the image were analyzed.

A total number of 61 texture features and shape parameters were extracted from the plaque segments using the following algorithms:

(i) **First Order Statistics (FOS)**, [4]

1) Mean value, 2) Median value, 3) Standard deviation, 4) Skewness, 5) Kurtosis.

(ii) **Spatial Gray Level Dependence Matrices (SGLDM)**, [5]

1) Angular second moment, 2) Contrast, 3) Correlation, 4) Sum of squares: variance, 5) Inverse difference moment, 6) Sum average, 7) Sum variance, 8) Sum entropy, 9) Entropy, 10) Difference variance, 11) Difference entropy, 12), 13) Information measures of correlation, 14) Maximal correlation coefficient.

For each feature the mean values and the range of values were computed and used as two different feature sets.

(iii) **Gray Level Difference Statistics (GLDS)**, [6]

1) Contrast, 2) Angular second moment, 3) Entropy, 4) Mean.

(iv) **Neighborhood Gray Tone Difference Matrix (NGTDM)**, [3]

1) Coarseness, 2) Contrast, 3) Business, 4) Complexity, 5) Strength.

(v) **Statistical Feature Matrix (SFM)**, [7]

1) Coarseness, 2) Contrast, 3) Periodicity, 4) Roughness.

(vi) **Laws Texture Energy Measures (TEM)**, [8], [9]

1) LL - texture energy from LL kernel, 2) EE - texture energy from EE kernel, 3) SS - texture energy from SS kernel, 4) LE - average texture energy from LE and EL kernels, 5) ES - average texture energy from ES and SE kernels, 6) LS - average texture energy from LS and SL kernels.

(vii) **Fractal Dimension Texture Analysis (FDTA)**, [10], [11]

$H^{(k)}$ parameter (Hurst coefficient) for resolutions $k=1, 2, 3, 4$.

(viii) **Fourier Power Spectrum (FPS)**, [6]

1) Radial sum, 2) Angular sum.

(ix) Shape Parameters

1) X - coord. maximum length, 2) Y - coord. maximum length, 3) Area, 4) Perimeter, 5) Perimeter²/Area.

The best features have to be identified and used for the classification of the carotid plaques. The distance between the two classes for each feature was computed as

$$dis = 1 - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}{|m_1 - m_2|} \tag{1}$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the mean values and σ_1 and σ_2 are the standard deviations of the two classes. The maximum possible distance value is 1, whereas negative values indicate overlap of the two classes. The features were ordered according to their interclass distance as tabulated in table I. The best features are the ones with the greatest distance and were selected to be used for the plaque classification.

3.4 Plaque Classification

Following the computer aided feature extraction, feature classification was implemented based on neural network technology. The use of artificial neural network (ANN) technology in image analysis has recently been shown. The advantages of artificial neural networks that make them so attractive to investigate are the following [12]: (i) exhibit adaptation or learning, (ii) pursue multiple hypothesis in parallel, (iii) may be fault tolerant, (iv) may process degraded or incomplete data, (v) make no assumptions about underlying data probability density functions and (iv) seek answers by carrying out transformations. The self-organising feature map (SOFM) classifier was used for the classification of carotid plaques into one of the following types: (i) Symptomatic because of ipsilateral hemispheric symptoms, and (ii) Asymptomatic because they were not connected with ipsilateral hemispheric events.

3.4.1 Self-Organising feature map algorithm

The SOFM is an unsupervised learning algorithm where the input patterns are freely distributed over the output node matrix [13]. The weights are adapted without supervision in such a way, so that the density distribution of the input data is preserved and represented on the output nodes. This mapping of similar input patterns to output nodes which are close to each other represents a discretisation of the input space, allowing a visualization of the distribution of the input data.

Fig. 3 Distribution of 37 carotid plaques (24 Symptomatic + 13 Asymptomatic) on a 7 x 7 SOFM using as input the fractal features H1, H2 and H3 which were found to have the highest discriminatory power (* = Symptomatic, o = Asymptomatic).

The output nodes are usually ordered in a two dimensional grid, and the weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood of the winning output node are adapted simultaneously. The neighborhood around the winning output node, decreases in size over time. The weights of the output nodes in the neighborhood are adapted with

$$w(t+1) = w(t) + \eta h(t) (x - w(t)) \quad (2)$$

where η is the learning rate ($0 < \eta \leq 1$) and $h(t)$ is a decreasing function which decreases with time. At the end of the training phase, the output nodes were labelled with the class of the majority of the input patterns of the training set, assigned to each node. In the evaluation phase, an input pattern was assigned to the output node with the weight vector closest to the input vector, and it was said to belong to the class label of the winning output node where it had been assigned.

4 RESULTS

A total of 37 (24 symptomatic + 13 asymptomatic) ultrasound images of carotid atherosclerotic plaques were examined. Fifty six different texture features and five shape parameters were extracted as described in section 3.3. The mean and standard deviation for all the plaques, as well as for the symptomatic and asymptomatic groups separately, were computed. Furthermore the distance between the two classes was computed as described in Eq. 1 and the features were ordered according to their interclass distance. Best features are the ones with the greatest distance. The results for the best texture features extracted using the FOS, NGTDM, SFM and FDFA algorithms are tabulated in table I. As it is shown in the table, for all features the distance is negative which means that the feature values of the two groups overlap. The best texture features were found to be the fractals H1, H2 and H3, whereas features like roughness, skewness and median gray level value have also been ranked with high interclass distance. Figure 3 illustrates the visualization of the distribution of the 37 plaques on a 7x7 SOFM. As input were used the fractals H1, H2 and H3.

Table I Statistical analysis of the best texture feature sets computed from 37 (24 symptomatic + 13 asymptomatic) ultrasound images of carotid atherosclerotic plaques. For each feature the mean and standard deviation were computed (i) for all the plaques, (ii) for the symptomatic group and (iii) for the asymptomatic group. Further the distance between the symptomatic and the asymptomatic groups was computed as described in section 3.3 and the features were ordered according to their interclass distance.

Nr	Texture Feature	All Plaques		Symptomatic		Asymptomatic		Distance $1 - \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}{ m_1 - m_2 }$	Rank Order
		Mean	Std	Mean m_2	Std σ_1	Mean m_2	Std σ_2		
<i>First Order Statistics (FOS)</i>									
1	Mean	32,258	19,672	28,965	15,694	38,337	24,283	-3,265	11
2	Median	18,562	20,58	14,441	16,263	26,169	25,058	-2,523	6
3	Stand. Deviation	38,01	11,16	37,529	10,563	38,898	12,137	-15,588	54
4	Skewness	2,357	1,104	2,567	1,162	1,971	0,863	-2,398	4
5	Kurtosis	11,699	8,054	13,039	9,002	9,224	5,056	-2,685	7
<i>Neighborhood Gray Tone Difference Matrix (NGTDM)</i>									
36	Coarseness	10,378	10,071	8,672	5,62	13,528	14,665	-3,177	9
37	Contrast	1,209	2,628	0,911	1,318	1,761	3,998	-5,251	27
38	Busyness	0,00024	0,00014	0,00014	0,00014	0,00011	0,00012	-8,745	39
39	Complexity	24446,9	14945,2	24869,7	15501,6	23666,3	13825,4	-23,371	56
40	Strength	982761	738230	104869	738556	861034	721976	-6,783	32
<i>Statistical Feature Matrix (SFM)</i>									
41	Coarseness	9,81	3,695	10,267	3,966	8,966	2,952	-4,317	18
42	Contrast	22,304	3,583	22,528	3,333	21,889	3,972	-10,432	43
43	Periodicity	0,592	0,052	0,586	0,055	0,603	0,043	-4,659	22
44	Roughness	2,333	0,091	2,351	0,094	2,301	0,074	-2,35	3
<i>Fractal Dimension Texture Analysis (FDFA)</i>									
51	H1	0,401	0,06	0,389	0,062	0,422	0,05	-2,423	5
52	H2	0,347	0,06	0,333	0,059	0,372	0,054	-1,931	2
53	H3	0,272	0,044	0,261	0,039	0,292	0,045	-1,696	1
54	H4	0,229	0,044	0,229	0,039	0,227	0,051	-42,405	59

The high degree of overlap in all features makes the separation and the classification of the two groups difficult. However an attempt was made to train the SOFM classifier with part of the images and evaluate it with the rest. For this purpose 20 (10 symptomatic + 10 asymptomatic) plaque images were used for training a 5x5 SOFM

classifier where the rest 17 (13 symptomatic + 4 asymptomatic) plaque images were used for evaluating the classifier. The classifier was trained and evaluated ten times using each time one of the ten feature sets described in section 3.3. All features were normalised by division with their mean values before used for classification. The best classification result was yielded by the fractals feature set and it was 65%. This result was further verified using three different bootstrap sets where in each set 20 different images were selected at random for training and 17 different images for evaluation. Because of the complexity of the problem and the high degree of overlap of the texture features it is necessary that the results to be verified with more images and more bootstrapping.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study a computer aided system using texture features and neural network technology is proposed for the classification of carotid plaques. Such a system will greatly help in enhancing the significance of noninvasive cerebrovascular tests in the identification of asymptomatic carotid stenosis at risk of stroke. A total number of 61 texture features and shape parameters were extracted from the carotid plaque images. The statistics for all the texture features extracted, indicate a high degree of overlap between the symptomatic and asymptomatic groups. This makes the separation and the classification of the two groups difficult. However features like the fractals, the roughness, skewness and median gray level contribute towards the identification of a group of patients with a high risk to have a stroke and which will benefit from a carotid endarterectomy. Due to the difficulty of the problem and the limited amount of the available data, the results have to be verified with more images from more patients.

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